

Article

Pneumonia associated with mechanical ventilation (VAP): prevention strategies

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Abstract: The pneumonia associated with mechanical ventilation (VAP) are respiratory infections in intensive care units and are associated with a high number of deaths. The goal of this article is to identify the best VAP prevention strategies. The use of additional instruments introduced orally or nasopharyngeally, such as endotracheal tubes, is a life-saving strategy, keeping the patient's breathing active when unable to do so independently. From the literature it emerges that a correct prevention and care management of the patient results in a reduction in the incidence of lung infections, but requires a specific knowledge of the techniques to be adopted. The healthcare professional must ensure that during the procedures all hygiene rules are respected and that there is no passage of pathogens from the operator to the patient or from one patient to another. It must be updated on the correct practices and the best materials to use. Through a review of the literature are reported the main bundles aimed at preventing the onset of VAP.

Keywords: VAP, infection, prevention.

Received:
Aprile, 2023
Accepted:
Julu, 2023
Published:
August, 2023

1. Pathogenesis and Epidemiology

Hospital infections of the lower respiratory tract are, in order of frequency, the third cause of infection, but are among the most frequently fatal: about 15% of all deaths from hospital infection are, in fact, directly attributable to hospital pneumonia. This complication arises from 8% to 28% of mechanically ventilated patients and carries a mortality risk of about 10% (range from 6% to 27%) with about 25,000 deaths attributable to VAP each year. Patients who develop VAP, on average, have a stay longer than 4 days in recovery. The cost per case of VAP is estimated at \$23,000 and the cumulative costs for the US healthcare system are high: from \$2.19 to \$3.17 billion per year. The wide range of these estimates is due to the lack of reliable and internationally accepted diagnostic criteria for diagnosing VAP[22].

In patients subjected to ventilation it is defined according to the following general criteria [18]:

presence, on x-ray examination, of a new and persistent lung infiltrate; purulent secretion; temperature 38°; leukocytosis (GB 10000/mmc); decompensated oxygenation. All these signs and symptoms may raise the suspicion of pneumonia associated with mechanical ventilation (VAP), since a more definite diagnosis can be made with the support of a positive blood culture or a pleural fluid culture, or a secretion obtained from the lower respiratory tract. The infection begins 48-72 hours after intubation. VAP occurs when the pathogen reaches the distal lung, colonizes it and gradually overcomes the host's defense.

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There are many reasons why the defense mechanisms of the patient in intensive care are reduced at the level of the respiratory tract, but the factors that directly predispose the patient to the colonization of the distal lung are mechanical ventilation and colonization of the oropharyngeal cavity and stomach. The GIVITI report (Italian Group for the Evaluation of Interventions in Intensive Care) of 2010 shows that about 70% of patients admitted to ICU undergo mechanical ventilation. The pathogenetic mechanism is linked to the presence of the orotracheal tube that reduces the natural defenses of the upper airways and promotes the formation of a biofilm, resulting in an increase in the bacterial load: the colonization of the aerodigestive tract and the contamination of the devices and the circuit connected to the artificial aerial way are the main pathogenetic mechanisms [8]. Micro-aspiration and inhalation are the transmission pathways most frequently involved in the development of VAP. Tracheal intubation predisposes to aspiration by weakening the natural barriers of the host, reducing local clearance and damaging the mucosa of the airways. A systemic review was carried out in the Pubmed Chocrane Library and Cinahl Plus databases using the PICO methodology (Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcomes). The question asked is: What evidence-based strategies are used to prevent VAP? The search strategy was based on the different combination of keywords used in six different search strings. The research provided 1743 documents: to be considered, the articles had to meet the following inclusion and exclusion criteria: year of publication from 2010 to 2017; experiments, observational studies, literature reviews and meta-analysis, quasi-experimental studies; setting: intensive care (polyvalent or specific) or resuscitation for adults. The eligibility criteria are represented by patients in intensive care who are placed with an endotracheal tube for mechanical ventilation; aged between 35 and 55 years and no classical risk factor for pathogens MDR (multidrug-resistant). The following were excluded: little or very specific documents compared to research questions; studies conducted in other hospital or extra-hospital areas; documents in non-English language or not having abstracts. The revision of the titles made it possible to select 88 titles that were subsequently subjected to a further selection that led to the elimination of duplicates (66 jobs). The remaining articles were evaluated through the reading of the abstract that allowed to select a total of 26. It highlighted the fundamental role of prevention and the main evidence-based strategies stressing the concept of interdisciplinarity. In particular, with regard to the first question, it emerged to open the centrality of the use of so-called bundles that delinea more specifically below [14].

2. Ebm Internet Lancet Online

The new document has been developed by a panel of experts from ERS (European Respiratory Society), ESICM (European Society of Intensive Care Medicine), ESCMID (European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases) and ALAT (Asociacion Latinoamericana del Trax). Respiratory medicine specialists with experience in the management of lung infections, intensive care specialists, microbiologists and methodologists with experience in reviewing clinical trials and developing guidelines were involved. In 2016 the American companies ATS (American Thoracic Society) and IDSA (Infectious Diseases Society of America) also published the latest update of their LG. However, the committee coordinated by Mr Torres considered that a different perspective was needed, given the differences between European and US approaches in different areas, such as the definitions of HAP and VAP and their diagnosis which is still a controversial issue, in particular as regards the role of quantitative cultures and bronchoscopic sampling.

In addition, new evidence has emerged in many contexts, including de-escalation studies (switching from early empirical broad spectrum to narrower spectrum antibiotic therapy or reducing the number of antibiotics), HAP bacteriology, the use of biological markers to reduce the duration of therapy and the resistance of some pathogens. Finally, a new contribution was also given by the Guidance for HAP/VAP trials issued by FDA and EMA. The levels of evidence and degrees of recommendation used in the new document follow the GRADE (Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation) methodology. This widely used procedure aims to develop recommendations in the context of guidelines for informed decisions. It is characterized by four levels of evidence: high, moderate, low and very low. Recommendations are classified as strong or weak after considering some factors, including the quality of the evidence and the relationship between desirable and undesirable consequences of the compared options.

Below are the bundles related to the preventive strategies of evidence-based nursing, where per bundle is defined a group of (few and simple) procedures or behaviors for which there is evidence of effectiveness. The correctly applied bundle in the care routine produces better results than the sum of the results of the individual procedures that compose it.

3. Bundle

Management of assisted ventilation pneumonia (VAP) and hospital acquired pneumonia (HAP): new international guidelines. An international committee of 15 experts and two methodologists has updated the guidelines (LG) on assisted ventilation pneumonia (VAP) and acquired in hospital (HAP).

3.1 Measures generals

They include standard precautions such as team education programs, hand decontamination (hand washing with soap and water or alcohol friction), use of barrier devices (gloves, lab coats) and implementation of microbiological surveillance protocols (Maselli, Restrepo, 2011).

3.2 Unnecessary handling of the circuit

Maselli et al., report how frequent changes and manipulations of the circuit can promote the onset of pneumonia, due to the facilitated contamination of the circuit or displacement of condensed fluids towards the airways. The meta-analysis conducted by Han et al., shows that those who receive a circuit change every 2 days compared to a replacement every 7 days, have a greater risk of developing the VAP (OR 1,928, 95% CI 1,080-3,443); moreover, comparing a change of the non-routine circuit with a change at intervals of 2 or 7 days, you get an OR 1,126 (0,793-1,599). There is a lower tendency to develop pneumonia when the circuit has changed at extended intervals, as well as resulting in lower economic expenditure. Auxiliadora-Martins et al., in a prospective study, focus on the role of heat and humidity exchangers (HME) concluding that they do not reduce the incidence of VAP, the duration of ventilation and the stay in intensive care.

3.3. Early extubation

Evaluation of possible extubation and daily cessation of sedation are part of the Institute of Healthcare Improvement (IHI) prevention bundle. Research indicates that the implementation of a wake up and breathe protocol hesitates in better outcomes of intubated patients, compared to standard approaches (Sedwick and Lance-Smith et al., 2012).

3.4 Suspension of sedation

The use of sedation suspensions has been shown to favor a faster weaning of patients from mechanical ventilation than when these techniques were not used. In addition, sedation suspensions reduce patient exposure and the resulting risk of VAP, as well as many other complications associated with mechanical ventilation are themselves considered safe. A study that examined a sedation protocol that specified daily sedative interruptions in combination with spontaneous breathing tests showed a reduction in ventilation days and the length of hospital stay. Although the group of patients undergoing the discontinuation of sedation had a higher rate of autoextubation, the percentage of patients requiring re-injection was similar in the pre- and post-surgery group. These results suggest that sedation suspensions should be part of all VAP prevention bundles.

3.5 Oral care

About 25 articles highlight the enormous importance of oral decontamination as a method of VAP prevention. Three articles indicate chlorhexidine at 0.12% concentration effective in the elimination of pathogens potentially related to the development of VAP, especially gram-negative. In the meta-analysis of Zhang et al., it was found that chlorhexidine positively affects the incidence of VAP (relative risk 0.59, $p < 0.00001$) and the beneficial effects of chlorhexidine at 0.12% (RR 0.53, $p < 0.00001$) compared to that at 2% concentration (RR 0.55, $p < 0.002$) recommending its use in intensive therapies.

3.6 Head of the bed

The use of the half-sitting position (backrest elevation) is the most important measure to be implemented in the early hours of mechanical ventilation. Mortality in intensive therapies is higher for patients in the supine position (30.2%), than in the half-sitting position (8.9%) (Grap and Munro et al., 2012). Sedwick et al., show that patients who spend most of their time in a $< 30^\circ$ The practice of elevating the bed head to prevent VAP has been recommended by several medical associations including the Canadian Critical Care Group Trials, the American Thoracic Society, the American Infectious Diseases Society, and the Centers for Disease Control Prevention. Specifically, the patients to whom this position benefits most, are those subjected to enteral nutrition since, compared to the supine position, gastric reflux and the consequent aspiration of gastric contents can be prevented (Maselli, Restrepo, 2011). Microaspiration may be due to the presence of gold/nasogastric probes used for enteral nutrition (Nseir and Zerimech et al., 2011). The systematic review conducted by Chen (2009) shows that intermittent nutrition does not affect the rate of colonisation of the airways. A 2011 systematic review of the effects of CHG that included 12 RCTs (2341 patients) further confirms previous findings. Relative risk of VAP after oral hygiene with CHG was reduced by 28% for all patients.

3.7 Prevention of biofilm formation

The colonization of the tube cuff, following the contamination of the oropharyngeal secretions or by gastric reflux (Fernandez, Levine, 2012), can lead to the formation of the biofilm, preventing the entry of anti microbial agents (Maselli, Restrepo, 2011). Three studies emphasize the importance of using a silver-coated endotracheal tube. In the review of Grap et al., it was found that in patients with silver coated tube the microbiological rate is lower than in patients with normal tube (4.8% CI 3.4-6.6 vs 7.5% CI 5.7-9.7%), however this does not statistically affect the duration of intubation, in intensive and hospital care, and the frequency or severity of adverse effects. It is important to note that although the cost of a silver-coated endotracheal tube is high (90 versus 2), the cost savings per case of VAP is 12,840 (Fernandez and Levine et al., 2012).

3.8 Pressure monitoring of the cannula cuff:

It requires a daily pressure check of the tracheal cuff using a pressure gauge. The pressure should be within a range of 20-30 cmh₂o. The tracheal cuff performs several functions, such as: ensuring the positioning of the endotracheal tube (avoiding dislocation), maintaining constant ventilation volumes, protecting the airways from possible inhalation of blood and saliva, limit trauma to the trachea mucosa. Over-inflation: decubitus, ischemic damage, tracheal stenosis, fistulas, malacia; under-inflation: dislocation (extubation), pneumonia ab ingestis, airflow, VAP (micro-aspiration and inhalation) prevent the hyper-production of mucus by proper hydration of the patient. On the other hand, the closed-loop suction system has a significantly higher cost compared to disposable probes, it needs to be replaced every 24/72h (or depending on the manufacturer's indications), requires a management that requires washing with pre-filled bottles of NaCl 0.9% after each wash, to ensure hygiene and patency.

3.9. Microaspiration of subglottic secretions

The sub-glottic suction tubes counteract the tendency of gold-nasal secretions and cellular debris to collect over the endotracheal tube cuff and under the vocal cords. This collection creates a breeding ground for microorganisms present in the nose-oropharyngeal tract, which leads to excessive proliferation and is one of the main causes of VAP. Some systems use a single suction port, while others use an active washing system with an input and output port to remove the secreted material. Aspiration of subglottic secretions is strongly recommended to reduce the risk of VAP by 49%, although there are no differences in mortality (Grap and Munro et al., 2012). Despite these benefits, some authors (Fernandez, Levine, 2012) are studying the possible consequences due to the application of this method, such as the formation of tracheal lesions or the stopping of the suction that occur in about 1/3 of the patients. An alternative method may be continuous oral aspiration of secretions (COS). Chow et al., (2012), evaluate its effectiveness in a study whose results show reduced ventilation time and incidence of VAP and underline the value of nursing staff in oral hygiene of the patient.

Disadvantages: high cost: they must be replaced every 48 hours; less effective in the removal of secretions because in part the air is also sucked out of the fan; increased levels of end-of-breath pressure during the insertion of the catheter.

Aspiration of endotracheal secretions

Aspiration of tracheal secretions is an essential technique in intubated and mechanically ventilated patients, This technique guarantees the patency of the airways by reducing the stasis of secretions that accumulate due to the lower effectiveness of the cough mechanism. The aspiration should not follow a precise frequency but should be performed according to a clinical need, the nurse must be able to recognize the signs for an endotracheal aspiration: 7,25, evident secretions in the endotracheal tube; frequent and sustained coughing; the presence of incidental respiratory sounds, desaturation due to secretions, increased peak ventilation pressure; onset of respiratory distress when airway patency is assessed. The level of aspiration carried out should be limited for the removal of secretions and should be performed as quickly as possible to avoid the occurrence of adverse effects such as mechanical trauma of the oral mucosa, bronchospasm and cardiac arrhythmias; In patients who also require oxygen support, it is recommended to perform hyperoxygenation before and after the aspiration procedure to avoid arterial blood dessaturation due to aspiration. The open circuit system is the traditional one that is also used in patients not mechanically ventilated and required disconnection from the ventilation circuit, but this practice is not recommended because the disconnect

from the fan creates a way of entry for pathogens and can increase the risk of occurrence of VAP. The closed circuit system does not need to disconnect from the fan, it is equipped with fittings to connect to the patient's endotracheal tube and the fan without interrupting the air flow, also has a washing line for the elimination of residual secretions and a valve that prevents reflux. Although the closed-loop system is the most recommended to avoid the onset of a VAP, it has been shown that the two suction modes do not have a significant difference in the incidence of fan pneumonia since even the closed-loop system can be colonized by microorganisms with the risk of self-fertilization.

Well preliminary studies have concluded that closed circuits reduce the incidence of respiratory infections, it remains controversial the effectiveness of these systems compared to those open to prevent VAP. The literature has reported, however, advantages in terms of safety: closed-loop aspiration would be preferable because it reduces the aerosolization of respiratory secretions and protects health professionals; closed circuits would also avoid hypotension, cardiac arrhythmias, increased intracranial pressure and desaturation during aspiration. The advantages of the closed circuit in terms of time and difficulty of nursing are uncertain. Available evidence for closed aspiration circuits suggests that the latter do not bring substantial benefits over open circuits in terms of VAP incidence, mortality and length of stay in ICU. Closed circuits may be associated with a longer duration of mechanical ventilation and a greater degree of colonisation of the respiratory tract.

In summary

Avoid unnecessary and harmful bronchoscopies, wash hands, wear gloves, choose a suitable gauge probe to avoid risks of secondary hypoxia at tube occlusion (maximum diameter 1/3 of the tube), it is advisable to hyperoxygenate the patient for about 30 seconds before performing bronchoscopy, removing and connecting the probe to the aspirator in an aseptic manner. Suction gently in a rotary way, rising upwards in 10-15 seconds, preventing hemodynamic consequences minimize local trauma, once reconnected the patient to the fan, Place the head of the bed between 30 and 45° and throw the material used among the special waste, avoiding contamination. Wash your hands. The appearance of an infectious complication in a patient in hospital has a high clinical impact, represents a failure of care and gives rise to countless consequences for both the patient and the hospital. For the patient, it means having to bear an additional infectious pathology, consequences in terms of temporary or permanent disability, any costs of home care, the loss of working days, or, at worst, the unfortunate outcome. For the hospital, it entails an increase in the cost of hospitalization for further diagnostic examinations and therapeutic interventions. Hospital infections are, at least in part, preventable. It has been shown that the adoption of care practices considered 'safe', alone, is able to prevent or control the transmission of infections, with a reduction of at least 35% of the frequency of these complications. Prevention can improve patient safety in intensive therapies. Prevention strategies, identified in the literature as collaborative problems, include the application of prevention bundles. The safety of care is a quality dimension that is essential and indispensable for advanced health systems today, which must be guaranteed to patients by professionals and health organizations and also publicly demonstrated. These are measures that, even in times of revision and cost reduction, must not be waived, because ensuring safety: it is a professional ethical duty towards patients; it is a social duty of health organisations vis-à-vis the societies that entrust them with resources to protect and promote their health; means making health systems sustainable: doing things right the first time costs less.

From the complexity of the preventive aspects it is clear that the multidisciplinary team is responsible for the implementation of preventive programs based on the evidence of effectiveness. From the literature it is clear that proper nursing care aimed at reducing the risk of lung infection incidence related to mechanical ventilation must consist of several aspects and nursing interventions.

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